

Assessing the future role of natural gas in Kenya's power system under uncertainty

Introduction

African countries are expanding their power system working towards development targets and climate goals¹. In the long term, the alignment between development and climate goals implies that African power systems are likely to be increasingly based on clean energy technologies^{2,3}. However, the pathway towards such systems remains uncertain and highly dependent on national circumstances^{1,2}. While energy transition modelling is becoming increasingly common across Africa, these analyses have often prioritised decarbonisation objectives without fully accounting for development priorities⁴. Moreover, energy planning can occur in institutional silos, with limited alignment between nationally determined contributions (NDCs) and national development plans (NDPs)⁵.

Energy system modelling has the potential to help bridge these disconnects by providing evidence to inform planning and policy decisions, and planning documents and modelling studies are already frequently used to guide investment strategies and policy design. However, uncertainty is rarely addressed systematically in such analyses. Deterministic models are typically applied to optimise decisions under a single set of assumptions or to simulate the effects of specific policy targets. A small number of scenarios is then used to explore alternative futures, often covering only a limited portion of the uncertainty space. As a result, key uncertainties may be underestimated, and modelling results may be contested where underlying assumptions are not widely trusted⁶.

These limitations have led to growing interest in approaches that explicitly account for uncertainty and involve stakeholders more directly in the modelling process. Participatory modelling approaches are increasingly recognised as important for ensuring that modelling outputs are policy-relevant and credible^{7,8}. At the same time, methods that systematically explore uncertainty, beyond a small set of scenarios, are needed to identify strategies that remain robust across a wide range of possible futures⁹. Such approaches may be particularly valuable in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where economic, technological and institutional uncertainties are often pronounced¹⁰.

Kenya exemplifies most of the trends and challenges outlined. The country has set ambitious targets for renewable energy deployment and electricity access, including a commitment to achieving a fully clean electricity system by 2030¹¹ while expanding the electrification of end uses¹². Looking towards 2050, solar and wind are expected to form the backbone of a predominantly renewable-based power system^{13,14}. This transition places increasing emphasis on system flexibility. With limited scope for further large-scale hydropower expansion and geothermal resources expected to provide relatively stable baseload capacity, meeting flexibility requirements is likely to depend on either natural gas generation, battery storage, or a combination of both.

Scenario-based modelling exercises frequently identify a role for natural gas as a flexible resource in Kenya's future power system. However, gas-fired peaking plants are typically built to meet reserve margin requirements rather than to operate at high load factors^{13,14}. This raises important questions about the feasibility and desirability of developing natural gas infrastructure, which would require investments in import facilities as well as transmission and distribution networks. At the same time, rapidly declining costs of battery storage raise concerns about potential lock-in effects associated with premature investment in gas infrastructure.

Methods

Robust Decision Making process

This analysis is structured around the Robust Decision Making (RDM) framework¹⁵ and four co-creation workshops conducted with planners from the Least Cost Power Development Plan (LCPDP) team between September 2024 and February 2026. The first workshop was held online, with the subsequent three conducted in person in Kenya.

RDM is an iterative and participatory approach designed to support decision making under deep uncertainty by exploring a wide range of futures and identifying strategies that perform robustly across them¹⁶. The implementation is built on a RDM workflow based on the OSeMOSYS modelling framework¹⁷, that has been adapted to the Kenyan power system context and the requirements emerged during the workshops and consultations with stakeholders.

The first part of the RDM workflow is centred around the definition of an XLRM matrix, which structures the problem definition. Here, X denotes the uncertainties, L the decision levers, R the relationships (i.e., the model of the power system), and M the metrics used to evaluate the performance of the strategy.

Uncertainties

The uncertainties considered are demand, capital costs, fuel costs, global discount rate, tech-specific discount rates^{16,18–26}, geothermal resources.

Demand

Demand projections and associated uncertainty ranges are derived from the LCPDP¹². The baseline corresponds to the reference scenario, while the uncertainty range spans from 80% of baseline demand, reflecting the low-demand scenario, to 280%, corresponding to the high-demand scenario defined in the LCPDP.

Capital cost

Capital cost assumptions are technology specific. Base year values are based on previous work^{13,14} and updated on the most recent local cost assumptions where necessary. In the case of batteries, costs are based on global averages based on data from the IEA²⁸, under the assumption of considering 4h lithium batteries. The lower end of capital cost projections for hydro, solar, wind and batteries are based on Way et al.²⁹

Fossil fuel prices

Natural gas import prices assumptions are based on historical gas market prices for Europe and Asia. Monthly data from the International Monetary Fund is obtained from the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis platform FRED^{30,31} and plotted in Figure 1. To reflect LNG market maturity, a baseline value of 10 USD/GJ is taken as a reference for the Kenyan case, corresponding to post-2015 market average. The uncertainty range is set between 4 USD/GJ and 22 USD/GJ, roughly corresponding to p5 and p95 values of the two datasets.

Figure 1 Monthly historical prices for Asia LNG and Europe gas markets over the period 2003-2026.

Geothermal potential

Additional geothermal resources currently identified are 3.5 GW, that constitutes the baseline upper limit on geothermal capacity that can be built by the model. Recent estimates suggest an actual upper limit for geothermal capacity of 10 GW¹². The full range of uncertainty hence spans 3.5-10 GW.

Cost of capital

The private cost of capital (CoC) is increasingly recognised as an important and influential parameter in capacity expansion modelling.³² In lower- and middle-income countries in particular, high CoC can significantly drive up the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) of capital-intensive renewable technologies, reducing their cost-competitiveness. For example, the LCOE of solar PV is 70% higher in Brazil than in Europe, despite similar capital costs and higher solar irradiance in Brazil, due to the higher weighted average CoC (WACC) in Brazil (13% versus 4%).³³ Several modelling studies find that CoC assumptions significantly affect the cost-optimal technology mix.^{34,35} In this study we therefore made reasonable effort to establish an evidence-based baseline and range of trajectories for private CoC in Kenya.

Robust empirical data for CoC is generally lacking.³⁵ This is both because CoC is often considered a trade secret and not disclosed, and because where data is available, its high country- and technology-specificity prevents generalisation.³⁵ This has led to the development of several methods to estimate CoC, four of which were applied to Kenya in multi-country studies. The IEA and IRENA collected CoC estimates through investor and expert surveys.^{32,36} As this approach is resource intensive and has to-date had limited country and technology coverage, Nato et al. and Hatton et al. instead modelled CoC.^{37,38} This involves the analysis of general financial market data, such as stock and bond prices, to approximate the constituent CoC components (base, country, equity, and technology risks and premiums).³⁵ IRENA combined the two approaches by constructing a CoC model which was subsequently recalibrated to expert estimates.³⁶ Finally, Wildgruber et al. modelled WACC, but rather than drawing on general financial data, optimised component values based on a global database of empirical and survey CoC data.³⁹

technologies by 2050. The worst-case scenario reflects deteriorating macroeconomic conditions or weakening concessional and de-risking support. In this scenario, CoC linearly increases to 15-16% while maintaining base year differences between technologies.

A summary of WACC assumptions is presented in Table 1. The first year of uncertainty was set to the model base year (2019) to introduce some uncertainty by 2025. Nominal WACC data provided by Hatton et al. were converted to real WACCs using the Fischer equation and a 2% inflation assumption.³⁹

Table 1. Real pre-tax weighted average cost of capital assumptions for the model base year and 2050.

	2019	2050	
		Lower bound	Upper bound
Geothermal	9.1%		15%
Hydro	8.3%		15%
Solar PV	8.7%		15%
Network	8.7%	1.6%	15%
Wind	7.4%		14%
Bioenergy	9.2%		16%
Nuclear	8.7%		15%
Battery	9.8%		16%

Interest accrued during construction (IDC) was also incorporated into the CoC. IDC is a capitalised cost and thus typically added to the capital cost. However, since it is dependent on technology CoC, it was simpler to implement in this RDM experiment by including in the CoC.

The construction finance factor, CFF , is a capital cost multiplier reflecting IDC.⁴⁵

$$CFF = \sum_{y=1}^C FC_y \cdot (1 + WACC)^{C+0.5-y}$$

Where FC_y is the fraction of capital spent in year y of the construction period, C is the construction duration in years, and y indexes each year of construction. $WACC$ during construction was assumed to be the same as during operation. The term $n + 0.5 - y$ assumes mid-year expenditure timing in line with the OSeMOSYS convention.

For each technology, an adjusted WACC was solved for which produces the same annuity when applied to the overnight capital cost as the real WACC applied to the CFF-adjusted capital cost:

$$CRF(WACC_{adjusted}) = CRF(WACC_{real}) * CFF$$

where CRF is the capital recovery factor and is used to annualise the capital cost and is given by:

$$CRF = \frac{1 - (1 + WACC)^{-1}}{1 - (1 + WACC)^{-L}}$$

where L is the operational life of the technology.

Construction timeline assumptions and CFF-adjusted WACCs are summarised in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively.

Table 2. Construction timeline assumptions, sourced from the Electric Power Research Institute.⁴⁶

Technology	Fraction of capital spent in each year before commissioning								Construction finance factor
	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
Gas CCGT					4%	17%	51%	29%	1.16
HFO						15%	44%	41%	1.13
Wind onshore							96%	4%	1.11
Solar PV								100%	1.04
Nuclear			15%	25%	25%	20%	10%	5%	1.35
Biomass					10%	25%	45%	20%	1.17
Geothermal			10%	15%	25%	30%	15%	5%	1.32
Small hydro						15%	44%	41%	1.11
Large hydro	1%	2%	9%	16%	22%	24%	20%	5%	1.28

Table 3. Real pre-tax weighted average cost of capital assumptions adjusted for interest during construction.

	2019	2050	
		Lower bound	Upper bound
Geothermal	13%	2.0%	28%
Small hydro	9%	1.7%	18%
Large hydro	9%	1.6%	17%
Solar	9%	1.6%	17%
Network	9%	1.6%	16%
Wind	9%	1.8%	18%
Bioenergy	11%	1.8%	21%
Nuclear	12%	1.8%	28%
Battery	11%	1.7%	19%

Levers

The policy levers considered correspond to the targets set by the Kenyan government and their representation within the LCPDP planning process.

Kenya has an announced target to achieve clean power by 2030⁴⁷, where the definition of clean includes natural gas-fired power plants. In this study, the target is assumed to be met by 2035, aligning with the timeline over which all fuel oil power plants are planned to retire under the LCPDP¹².

Despite recent government announcements⁴⁸, natural gas power plants are assumed to become operational no earlier than 2031. This timeline remains a strongly optimistic assumption for power production from open-cycle gas turbine cycle in first-of-a-kind contexts. Senegal's case show that a fast-track FSRU route can bring gas into a country 2–3 years after project agreements⁵⁰. However, power production has been to date only based on a floating dual-fuel reciprocating engine, with production from gas turbine plant expected to start only in 2026, seven years after the publication of the Government's power-to-gas strategy⁵².

Natural gas plants start producing in 2031 reflects a planning process starting today. To assess the effect of any delayed strategy in the adoption of natural gas or delays in the execution of the plan, we

consider two additional scenarios where natural gas adoption is postponed of five and ten years respectively.

Relationships

The model used is the Kenya power system model^{13,14}, developed within the OSeMOSYS framework⁴⁹. Several changes have been introduced to adapt the model to this application.

First, the number of technologies is reduced. Previous versions of the model include a detailed representation down to individual power plants. This level of granularity is unnecessary for the present analysis, and technologies are aggregated to reflect only meaningful differences in resource characteristics. For example, the number of geothermal technologies was reduced from 52, corresponding to single unit power plants, to 7, representing major geothermal sites with similar steam conditions and cost structure. This aggregation reduces model size and, in turn, the computational burden of the RDM experiment.

Second, the underlying OSeMOSYS equations are modified to explicitly represent future changes to the technology-specific cost of capital and associated uncertainties. This is implemented by introducing technology specific-discount rates, drawing on a more recent OSeMOSYS formulation⁴⁷, and extending them to vary over time. To the authors' knowledge, this constitutes the first application of OSeMOSYS with time-dependent, technology-specific discount rates, and directly reflects the call to improve the representation of financing conditions in energy system models^{10,53}.

Third, a capacity constraint is introduced for solar and wind resources that is directly linked to total system demand. This enables the enforcement of N-1 security criteria¹⁴ under conditions of high demand variability. The constraint is particularly relevant for wind resources, as it prevents excessive concentration of capacity in high-capacity-factor regions, thereby avoiding unrealistic grid configurations.

Fourth, natural gas open cycle gas turbine (OCGT) capacity is linked to natural gas import capacity. The constraint ensures that for each unit of OCGT installed, sufficient import capacity is also deployed to enable at least 5% annual utilisation. This prevents the model from installing gas-fired capacity without the corresponding fuel supply infrastructure, while avoiding any direct constraint on the plant's actual operating profile.

Fifth, due to the aggregated temporal representation of the model, peak demand is underestimated by approximately 14% relative to the real system. To account for this and ensure a more conservative treatment of variable renewable energy expansion, the reserve margin is increased by an additional 15%, reaching a total of 125%. At the same time, the derating factor defining the contribution of each technology to the reserve margin is set to 0% for solar and a conservative 10% for wind.

Metrics

Metrics are the indicators against which strategies are tested. The key metric considered here is the presence of natural gas in the system by 2050. We define it as a yes/no parameter with value 1 if any level of capacity is installed in 2050 and 0 if it is not.

Other metrics monitored are the annual CO₂ emissions and Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE). The former is a direct OSeMOSYS output, while the latter is obtained from new builds (AIC), annual fixed and variable operating costs (VarCost and FixedCost), and an annualised residual capacity term (ResAIC).

$$LCOE_y = \frac{\sum_t AIC_{t,y}^{roll} + \sum_t VarCost_{t,y} + FixedCost_{t,y} + \sum_t ResAIC_{t,y}}{AnnualDem_y}$$

Where:

$$AIC_{t,y}^{roll} = \sum_{b=\max(1,y-n_t+1)}^y Inv_{t,b} \cdot CRF(r_{t,b}, n_t)$$

$$ResAIC_{t,y} = ResCap_{t,y} \cdot CapCost_{t,BY} \cdot CRF(r_{t,BY}, n_t)$$

$$CRF = \frac{1 - (1 + r)^{-1}}{1 - (1 + r)^{-n}}$$

Vulnerability analysis

The vulnerability analysis is built based on two machine learning algorithms for scenario discovery, Classification and Regression Trees (CART), and Patient Rule Induced Method (PRIM).

CART is a method to progressively split the data into groups with increasingly similar outcomes based on simple decision rules; it partitions the input space through a sequence of binary splits that maximise class separation at each node. Our implementation is based on the DecisionTreeClassifier function in scikit-learn⁴⁸. We define a hyperparameter grid for the decision tree and then use grid search with cross-validation to identify the combination of parameters that performs best on the classification task. In practice, the algorithm trains many candidate trees, evaluates them using a scoring method, and keeps the best-performing one as the final model. Hyperparameters include max depth of the tree, minimum number of leaves and splits, and splitting criteria.

PRIM is a scenario discovery algorithm that iteratively identifies regions of the input space associated with a target outcome. It operates through a peeling process, progressively restricting the domain to increase the density of cases of interest while maintaining a good level of coverage. Peeling is followed by a pasting phase that relaxes overly restrictive bounds. Our implementation is based on the EMA workbench Python library⁵⁵, using a density threshold of 50% and default values of 5% for minimum mass (i.e., the minimum share of the dataset that the final domain must contain) and peel and paste alphas (regulating the aggressiveness of peeling and pasting phases).

Both CART and PRIM are applied to identify the conditions under which the binary outcome of zero natural gas capacity in the system by 2050 occurs. In both cases, the analysis requires the definition of a set of input features describing each model run, derived by aggregating or filtering model inputs for each scenario. Most features use the value of input parameters in 2050, to capture the full uncertainty range. They include total electricity demand, technology-specific capital costs for geothermal, nuclear, natural gas, batteries, solar, wind, and fuel prices. Financing conditions are represented through both a global discount rate and technology-specific discount rates.

Results and discussion

Despite the wide range of uncertainties considered, clear patterns emerge in the projected capacity mix. Figure 3 shows that wind and geothermal form the backbone of Kenya's future power system. While geothermal is deployed at comparatively lower capacity levels, it provides baseload generation. Batteries show a similarly consistent role, co-deployed with wind, geothermal, and solar, to enhance VRE utilisation and provide system flexibility.

All three technologies show a relatively stable level of penetration in time in the system. This is illustrated by comparing the evolution of installed capacity (blue boxplots) with the capacity-to-peak-demand ratio (orange boxplots). Although projected demand is a major source of uncertainty and installed capacities span a wide range, all three technologies show a clear upward trend. By contrast, when expressed relative to the annual peak demand, their role appears more stable, as reflected in the median values. Wind capacity typically ranges between 60% and 80% of peak demand, batteries around 80%, and geothermal around 40%.

In contrast, solar, hydro and natural gas display more differentiated trends. Solar deployment increases markedly after 2040, both in absolute terms and relative to peak demand. This shift reflects not only projected declines in solar generation costs, but also reductions in battery costs, as BESS contribute to alleviate flexibility constraints and compensate its lack of contribution to reserve margins, as well as balancing daily mismatch between production and demand. Slower uptake of grid-connected solar, alongside a more prominent role for wind is consistent with recent capacity mix developments in Kenya⁵⁶. However, official figures underestimate the overall contribution of solar to system growth, as has been driven in part by captive and behind-the-meter installations⁵⁷.

Hydro currently represents a key component of the Kenya's power mix, with however limited scope for further expansion¹². The results suggest that the remaining available potential is largely exploited, but its relative contribution to the system declines over time. Despite its relatively modest capacity, hydropower is expected to retain a critical role in providing firm baseload generation alongside geothermal as VREs scale up.

Natural gas power plants exhibit a significantly less consistent role across the range of futures considered, with more than three quarters of runs showing no installed capacity. However, when gas plants are cost competitive, their capacity can reach up to 10 GW, contributing to system flexibility. When deployed, their role increases over time, both in absolute terms and relative to the system, reflecting rising flexibility requirements in a power system with growing shares of VREs. At the same time, the conditions under which this outcome emerges are limited, pointing to the risks associated with investing in gas infrastructure relative to alternatives such as batteries, whose role is consistently robust across futures. From a planning perspective, it is hence important to identify the drivers of natural gas adoption and assess the robustness of expansion strategies that do not rely on gas. This is particularly relevant given Kenya's current stage of power system development, as the absence of existing import, transmission, and distribution infrastructure for natural gas increases the risks and potential lock-in associated with gas-based pathways.

Figure 3 **Installed capacity and capacity to peak demand ratio for key technologies.** Each subplot shows the range of installed capacity (blue, left axis) per technology per year over the entire set of futures modelled, as well as the ratio between installed capacity and peak demand (orange, right axis). The blue boxplots give a reference for the absolute installed capacity, while the orange ones the relative weight of the technology with respect to the size of the system.

Scenario discovery methods are used to identify the conditions under which natural gas power plants become a cost-effective source of system flexibility.

Figure 4 shows the presents the main drivers identified by CART analysis. The most influential parameter is the cost of batteries storage by 2050. When battery costs fall below approximately 800 USD/kW, none of the modelled futures show investments in natural gas capacity. The first split alone captures around three quarters of all runs. This threshold is broadly consistent with current cost estimates, with the IEA reporting global battery costs in the range 600-800 USD/kW²⁸. Notably, this refers to technology costs alone and does not incorporate financing conditions.

Subsequent splits highlight the role of relative financing conditions across technologies. Improved financing terms for natural gas infrastructure increase its likelihood of deployment within the remaining quarter of modelled futures, while under current – or even slightly worsening – financing conditions for clean energy technologies (here proxied by wind), natural gas is not adopted. This suggests that sustained access to concessional finance for clean technologies could reinforce the role of batteries as the primary source of system flexibility.

Figure 4 Classification tree highlighting key thresholds in parameters influencing natural gas adoption in 2050. Starting from the top, the root split (box) identifies the most influential parameter in the runs with and without some natural gas capacity in Kenya's power system in 2050 and its threshold. Samples give the share of total runs falling in the corresponding node, value the relative weight of runs without gas (first value) and with some gas (second value). The colour of the node is associated to its class. Orange nodes indicate a set of runs where most of the runs have no natural gas in the system, while blue nodes indicate that most of the runs have some natural gas in the system. The darker the colour the closer the node to be fully made of runs of one class or the other.

Results from the PRIM analysis reinforce these findings. Figure 5 shows that futures with natural gas capacity in 2050 are strongly associated with higher battery costs, as indicated by the density of blue dots in this region of the parameter space (first row of subplots in the Figure). Other parameters exhibit broader distributions across their uncertainty ranges, suggesting a more conditional influence. Among these, financing conditions for both natural gas infrastructure and clean technologies (here proxied by battery storage) emerge as the next most relevant drivers. A secondary role is also observed for wind capital costs and geothermal financing conditions, the latter reflecting the importance of capital-intensive baseload technologies whose deployment is sensitive to exploration risks and cost of capital.

Figure 5 *Pairwise distributions of input features and their association with natural gas outcomes.* Plots on the diagonal show the density estimates of the feature in the corresponding column. Off-diagonal panels show bivariate scatter plots (above the diagonal) and the same data but through density contour (below the diagonal). Points are coloured by model outcome (orange: runs without natural gas capacity by 2050; blue: runs with natural gas). Red boxes highlight regions of the feature space identified by the classification tree as associated with the presence of natural gas.

Conclusions and policy recommendations

A key advantage of adopting an exploratory modelling approach for planning is that insights are stress-tested across a wide range of plausible futures, thereby improving their robustness. Incorporating uncertainty should therefore not be viewed as reducing clarity, but as strengthening the basis for strategic decision-making under conditions where key system drivers remain uncertain.

At the same time, modelling is inherently a decision-support tool rather than a substitute for policy choices. The results indicate that battery storage emerges as a robust option for providing system flexibility, particularly in light of ongoing global cost reductions. However, this does not imply that batteries are universally optimal across all futures, nor that alternative flexibility options can be disregarded. Rather, it suggests that strategies centred on battery deployment are less sensitive to adverse conditions than those relying on natural gas, especially in the absence of established gas infrastructure.

Realising this battery-centred pathway depends critically on the investment environment. Ensuring access to affordable finance is central, as cost of capital strongly influences the competitiveness of capital-intensive technologies such as batteries. In parallel, enabling conditions must be addressed,

including the development of appropriate regulatory frameworks, the strengthening of technical capabilities, and the establishment of supply chains required to support large-scale deployment.

A strategy centred on battery storage for flexibility would also avoid investment in new fossil fuel infrastructure for gas import and power generation, thereby limiting exposure to global gas price volatility. Recent market developments have illustrated the scale of such volatility, with sharp and sustained increases around periods of geopolitical tension. This volatility affects not only price levels but also the availability of LNG cargoes, which are redirected across markets in response to price signals, increasing supply uncertainty for import-dependent systems.

While the conclusions from this analysis point strongly towards batteries as a key enabler of flexibility, further considerations remain important. Natural gas infrastructure is rarely developed solely for power generation, with its economics typically relying on demand aggregation across multiple sectors, most notably industry in the Kenyan context. This may strengthen the case for investment in gas infrastructure, but also risks underestimating system-wide lock-in effects if cross-sector demand is used to justify capital-intensive infrastructure. At the same time, in an import-dependent system with constrained supply, power generation may compete with higher-value or less easily substitutable industrial uses. Industrial heat and feedstock uses are harder to electrify in the short term than power generation⁵⁸, increasing the opportunity cost of allocating gas to the power sector.

Further analysis is required to ensure that flexibility needs can be adequately met in the battery-focused systems identified. Emerging evidence from global power systems increasingly demonstrates the role of batteries in providing flexibility services²⁸. However, more detailed power system modelling could help ensure the operational feasibility of futures with high levels of BESS deployment.

Finally, additional flexibility options on the demand side have not been explored and could further strengthen the case for avoiding reliance on natural gas. These include leveraging flexible demand from emerging loads, such as electric vehicles⁵⁹, green hydrogen⁶⁰, or data centres⁶¹, as well as demand response for large commercial and industrial users, including cement production, tea processing, horticulture cold chains connected at medium and high voltage levels.

Acknowledgements

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme, funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

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